

Application of Nuclear Quadrupole Resonance in chemical compounds with special reference to molecular complexes (charge-transfer complex)

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Abstract : Both chemists and physicists use Nuclear Quadrupole Resonance (NQR) technique as frequently as NMR. Considering the vast range, this review is confined to the field of molecular complexes (charge transfer complexes), which is of great interest to chemists. This review encompasses both the theoretical studies and experimental observations of NQR in molecular complexes.

Keywords : Nuclear Quadrupole Resonance spectra (NQR), molecular complexes, ^{35}Cl NQR studies.

1. Introduction

Hyperfine interaction-especially quadrupole interaction is an indispensable tool for the determination of molecular structure and finds applications in various branches of chemistry.

The experimental study of nuclear quadrupolar interactions is often used as a powerful tool for characterizing different atomic sites in a given sample and obtaining information about local symmetry, coordination and structural centers in solids. In the case of pure electric-quadrupole interaction, the measured quantities are the quadrupole couple constant $V_Q = eQV_{33}/h$ and the asymmetry parameter $(V_{11} - V_{22})/V_{33}$; here V_{ii} ($i = 1, 2, 3$) are the components of the diagonalized electric field gradient (EFG) tensor with the convention $V_{33} > V_{22} > V_{11}$. In this way V_{33} is the major principal component of the EFG tensor. The EFG is measured via its interaction with the nuclear quadrupole moment Q of a suitable probe atom (generally an impurity in the system under study) by different techniques such as Mössbauer spectroscopy, NMR or NQR or Perturbed Angular Correlation (PAC)¹⁻³. Among these, NQR is specially significant.

The value of nuclear quadrupole interaction in the study of molecular structure and dynamics is very much appreciated as new techniques are developing. There is an increasing number of solid state nuclear magnetic resonance studies of quadrupole splitting using both magic

angle spinning and two dimensional Fourier transform methods; there is an wide-spread use of quadrupole interactions in the study of phase transitions and experiments which exploit the fact that nuclear quadrupole resonance is susceptible to dynamic effects, for both frequencies and the relaxation times are affected and provide information on different regions of the spectral density distribution⁴. Before the term "multinuclear" became common, quadrupole resonance spectroscopists had clearly demonstrated the wide range of quadrupolar nuclei that could be studied. Apart from the wide range of work on halogens (especially Cl) and nitrogen, recent experiments have included work on

^6Li ($i=1$), ^{33}S , ^{83}Kr , ^{93}Nb , ^{139}La , ^{167}Er , ^{181}Ta and ^{209}Bi . Even the "last of the halogens" ^{19}F has succumbed to investigation, in this case, by means of perturbed angular correlation measurements. Sensibility have considerably increased by double resonance techniques; thus the detection of signals from ^2H (0.016%) and ^{17}O (0.037%) in natural abundance has become almost routine. The theoretical interpretation of nuclear quadrupole interactions in solids has advanced. In molecular solids, hydrogen-bonding shifts are well reproduced and in ionic salts the question of partial covalence is explored.

The technique of line narrowing, which has such a dramatic impact on NMR in solids has also been applied to quadrupole resonance studies. By increasing the speed

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with which the magnetic field may be changed, the existence of "quadrupole dips" in biological systems has been observed.

Considering the wide range of applications of NQR in different areas, this review is confined to the application of NQR in molecular complexes or charge transfer complexes.

2. Charge transfer complexes

The term "charge transfer complex" was introduced by Mulliken⁵ in 1950 in his explanation of the observation by Benesi and Hildbrand⁶ of a new absorption band in a solution of benzene and iodine dissolved in *n*-heptane. The observed band did not appear in the spectra of either benzene or iodine. Mulliken stated that the colour of such organic molecular complexes "may be due to an intermolecular charge transfer process during light absorption". These early experimental and theoretical investigations signaled the beginning of a period of intense interest in the properties of donor acceptor complexes.

A particularly thorny question concerns the relative importance of charge transfer and electrostatic forces in the ground state of complexes such as $C_6H_6-I_2$. While Mulliken's early work successfully explored the early charge transfer model, more recent works by Hanna⁷ and by Stiles⁸ have emphasized the electrostatic considerations e.g. the quadrupole-induced dipole interactions in $C_6H_6-I_2$.

The direct connection between nuclear quadrupole coupling constant and charge distribution in a molecule leads to the expectation that the NQR frequency should shift owing to molecular complex formation through charge transfer interaction⁹.

3. Experimental studies ^{35}Cl as probe

Basu and Ghose¹⁰ studied a number of molecular complexes where the donor molecules have chlorine as well as a number of complexes where the acceptor molecules have chlorine as a probe. The direct connection between nuclear quadrupole coupling constant and charge distribution in a molecule leads to the expectation that the NQR frequency should shift owing to molecular complex formation. Maksyutin *et al.*¹¹ found a linear relation between ^{35}Cl NQR shift and ionization energy of donor in complexes of picryl chloride with aromatic hydrocarbons. Although various workers have suggested from time to time that it is desirable to extend the measurements to stronger complexes¹², the first systematic investigation

on strong complexes was made by Basu and her coworkers¹³. Spectrophotometric investigations have shown that chloranil forms fairly strong complexes with polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons¹⁴. The NQR frequencies of these complexes were measured on a super regenerative spectrometer NQR 40 manufactured by Electronic Corporation of India. These measurements showed that there was an approximate linear relation between ($^{35}Cl \mu \text{ sec}$) and energy of the topmost filled π -MO of the hydrocarbons (donors here) in chloranil hydrocarbon systems at 295 K. Owing to crystal field effects, quite a number of resonance signals were obtained at 77 K from systems containing chemically equivalent chlorine atoms. At 295 K, however one line was obtained. At that temperature the line was less intense and about 0.006μ wide. In these complexes the quadrupolar nucleus (^{35}Cl) was attached to the acceptor molecule. Theoretical consideration Maksyutin *et al.*¹¹ shows that if ^{35}Cl be on the donor molecule, Δv should be negative, but they had not given any experimental evidence in support of their prediction. In this paper Basu¹⁵ had measured the NQR frequency of ^{35}Cl in the charge transfer complexes of *p*-dichlorobenzene as donor and *s*-trinitrobenzene, picric acid, pyromellitic dianhydride and tetracyanoquinodimethane as acceptors. A linear relation was obtained between NQR shift and the charge transfer interaction energy $h\nu$ which is related to the ionization energy of the donor (I), electron affinity of the acceptor (E) and the ione-pair stabilization energy Δ by the Mulliken relation, $h\nu = I - E - \Delta$, ν being the frequency of optical charge transfer transition. They concluded that Maksyutin explanation for the NQR shift in these molecular complexes was not sufficient although a linear relation between Δv and charge transfer interaction obtained by optical method exists.

4. Role of forces other than charge transfer

In a subsequent work Basu and Ghose¹³ reported a number of other systems such as *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-chloroaniline with tetracyanoquinodimethane, picric acid, pyromellitic dianhydride and *s*-trinitrobenzene, and chloranilic acid, and tetrachlorophthalic anhydride with benzene, naphthalene, anthracene and pyrene. Maksyutin¹¹ investigated ^{35}Cl NQR for twenty molecular compounds of picryl chloride with substituted aromatic molecules and the upward shift of (^{35}Cl) was explained by assuming charge transfer as the sole reason whereas Basu and Ghose's observation showed that although polynuclear

hydrocarbons form stronger complexes the upward and the downward shifts from charge transfer force only were not corroborated. They concluded that in addition to charge transfer force, some other forces are there. Thus the presence of two nitrogen groups *ortho* to chlorine atom in picryl chloride prevents the approach of the donor and acceptor molecules. So the complex formation will depend not only on charge transfer but also on steric factor for the picryl chloride complexes. In addition they presumed that though electrostatic effects between non translationally equivalent molecules cancels out, the crystal field effect would cause a forward shift in the ^{35}Cl NQR frequency in weakly dipolar molecular crystal, irrespective of whether the chlorine atom is located in the donor or acceptor part of the complex. Thus they concluded that in solid molecular complexes electrostatic effect is much more prominent than any effect arising from charge transfer interaction. Here the conclusion drawn was that NQR shift in donor acceptor complexes was indirectly related to charge transfer interaction. In a subsequent paper Das and Basu⁴ studied the effect of the presence of chlorine in both the donor and acceptor (at the same time) on the NQR shift. The donors they had studied were *p*-dichlorobenzene, *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-chloroaniline and acceptors were chloranil DDQ, tetrachlorophthalic anhydride, chloranilic acid and *p*-chloronitrobenzene. They concluded that although NQR shift bears a linear relationship with ionization potentials of the donors thereby proving the charge transfer criteria, the contribution of various types of spatial interactions play a significant role. The magnitude of this contribution will be determined by the geometric structure of the complex which does contribute to the change in field gradient. Moreover crystallographic effects must not be ignored as it is well known that crystal field effects frequently shift quadrupole frequency by ± 200 kHz.

Townes and Dailey's method¹⁶ has been applied to relate NQR frequencies to the ionicity of σ -bonds. Maksyutin *et al.* studied the molecular compounds of picryl chloride with substituted aromatic molecules. Weiss's suggestion¹⁷ that the NQR frequency should shift due to molecular complex formation through charge-transfer interaction has been well demonstrated with molecules having quadrupolar nucleus either in the acceptor or in the donor or in both at the same time by Basu and coworkers as given above. Basu reported her observations on *p*-chloronitrobenzene and *ortho*-chloronitrobenzene as ac-

ceptors with different hydrocarbons as donors¹⁵. Following Mulliken and considering that the electric field gradient (EFG) at the atom in question is determined mainly by its *p*-electron density, Basu considered that the change in the gradient (in the system under considerations) as a result of charge transfer consists of

$$q_A = b^2 / (1 + s^2) \Sigma c_{A,t}^2 q_t \text{ (for the acceptor) and}$$

$$q_D = -[1 - a^2 + b^2 S^2 / (1 + S^2)] \Sigma c_{D,r}^2 q_r \text{ (for the donor)}$$

Thus the change in gradient¹⁸ is determined by the degree of charge transfer (*b*), its density (c^2) at the atom in question and the type of atomic orbital participating in the charge transfer. The overlap integral *S* of the interacting MOs can be neglected in the majority of cases. Under these conditions, the relative change in the EFG (or the relative frequency shift) will be

$$\Delta q_{zz} / q_{zz} = \Delta v / v = -b^2 / 2(1 + S^2)$$

Thus, in general, the relationship obtained leads to the conclusion that Δv as a result of complex formation is directly proportional to the degree of charge transfer.

Since the charge transfer takes place between π -molecular orbital of the donor and the acceptor, an increase in the π electron density on the molecule of the later should lead to a high Δv of ^{35}Cl in acceptors. A direct check of these relations was not possible since the parameters b^2 , c^2 and *S* were unknown. However, it was possible to check the linearity of above two relations.

The degree of charge transfer is directly related to the ionization potential of the donor. Therefore, the presence of a linear correlation between Δv of ^{35}Cl in these compounds would suffice to confirm the charge transfer character of these complexes. The formation of the complex was conditioned by a transfer of charge from the higher occupied MO of the donor to the lower free MO of the acceptor, which would change the EFG on the atoms of the interacting molecules. This was an electronic factor. But when the donor and acceptor molecules approached one another, various types of spatial interactions begin to play a significant part, thereby contributing to the change in the EFG. The magnitude of this contribution would be determined by geometric factors.

Frequency changes in these molecules might primarily be due to changes in electron density on the π and σ -orbital of the Cl atom. The EFG change considered upto now takes into account only π -orbital changes.

5. Ionicity studies

The covalency of the C-Cl bond may be calculated following Townes and Dailey's¹⁶ (T-D) theory by the relation,

$$(eqQ/h)_{exp} = (1 - i) (eqQ/h)_{atom}$$

where i is the ionic character of the bond and therefore $(1 - i)$ is the covalent character of the bond and $(eqQ/h)_{atom}$ is the NQR frequency of atomic chlorine (109.7 MHz). In resonance terms following Townes and Dailey's method, bonding in these complexes may be described as a hybrid of a pure covalent bond and a pure ionic bond

$$eqQ = (1 - i) (R-Cl) + i(R^+ - Cl^-)$$

that is ionicity meant the magnitude of the dipole moment of the bond. In the calculation of i the fractional ionic character therefore amounts to estimating the extent of σ -electron density change on the chlorine atom in an R-Cl bond. The T-D analysis suggests that the dipole moment of the C-Cl bond will increase in the donor and decrease in the acceptor on the charge transfer complex formation. This contention appears to hold fairly well in these complexes. However the author did not claim any generality because the presence of dipolar and multipolar interaction did exist in the charge transfer complexes, which definitely affect the bond character of C-Cl bond.

In line with the above analysis Basu¹⁹ calculated the ionicity of a series of molecular complexes. As expected, the data for chloranilic acid, tetrachlorophthalic anhydride and chloranil (acceptors) show that the ionicity decreases as these go into complexation. The same is true for *p*-dichlorobenzene, *p*-chloroaniline and *p*-chlorophenol. The ionicity increases as they go for complexation with DDQ, chloranil, tetrachlorophthalic anhydride, chloranilic acid and *p*-chloronitrobenzene as donors whereas a few others (vide Table 1) show an opposite effect. Thus a perfect generality cannot be claimed. The discrepancy may arise due to the presence of dipolar and multipolar interaction in the crystals of charge transfer complexes. This will considerably affect the bond character of C-Cl bond because of the change in potential gradient at Cl atom. This arises also from dipole induced dipole interaction. While calculating the dipole moment, the geometry of the complexes should play a dominant role as well.

6. Low temperature study

In a later paper Basu²⁰ reported NQR frequencies of a number of molecular complexes at liquid nitrogen temperature. As was shown earlier, although the electronic factor possesses systematic character the geometrical factors and crystal field effects are more or less accidental and hence the superposition of all these factors becomes irregular. The NQR signals of different donors, acceptors and their molecular complexes at room temperature (295 K) and at liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K) were measured. All the molecular complexes as well as the acceptors (chloranil) show two to three lines at liquid nitrogen temperature while they give only one line in the NQR spectra at room temperature.

The results on molecular complexes showed that both downward and upward shifts of the resonance frequencies occur as the temperature was decreased from room temperature to liquid nitrogen temperature. X-Ray studies on the crystal structure of aromatic hydrocarbons and tetrahalopara benzoquinones were not very conclusive. As the crystals suffered massive damage under X-ray irradiation, Wiessenberg photographs could not be taken for a complex crystal structure analysis. Information from oscillating photography shows that the donor and acceptor molecules are not in perfect alignment but rather tilted from the C-axis. Thus the appearance of two line spectra for the complexes may be assigned to two ³⁵Cl nuclei differently aligned to the carbon atom.

7. Theoretical studies

Very little theoretical studies have been made as yet. There are some CNDO/2 and as well as some *ab initio* calculations on some systems. Thus Habeeb²¹ reported nuclear quadrupole resonance and molecular orbital studies in H-bonded complexes of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzoic acid. Nuclear quadrupole resonance in nitro compounds had also been studied by a number of authors from time to time and reported elaborately²². In 1997 in an International Symposium on Nuclear Quadrupole Interaction, Hagelberg and Das²³ reported evaluation of 57m Fe Quadrupole moment from Hartree-Fock calculations. Jaszuxnski and Rizzo²⁴ reported *ab initio* study of nitrogen-14 nuclear quadrupole coupling and NMR line widths in some azoles. *Ab initio* calculations in halogen nuclear quadrupole coupling constants in non-axially symmetric molecules were reported by Palmer and Blairfish²⁵. The same authors reported the comparison of *ab initio* calculations which include correlation with experiment on the

same systems. Rama Pravu *et al.*²⁶ reported an experimental and theoretical investigation of nuclear quadrupole resonance of ¹²⁷I in orthoperiodic acid at 296 K. The same authors²⁷ reported an evaluation of EFG at the ⁷⁹Br site due to BrO₂ radicals in Zn(BrO₃)₂·6H₂O, Cd(BrO₃)₂·2H₂O and Sr(BrO₃)₂·H₂O. A CNDO/2 and INDO²⁸ methods were applied to evaluate EFG parameters in XO₃⁻ ions (X = Cl, Br, I). A review article on Nuclear Quadrupole Resonance and relaxation and another on nuclear quadrupole interactions in solids were published by Smith^{29,30}. Matshshita *et al.* discussed the charge resonance and charge transfer interactions in naphthalene³¹. Basu *et al.*³² applied the semi-empirical quantum mechanical program MOPAC and AM1 method to a number of charge transfer complexes of aromatic hydrocarbons with chloranil. The NQR values calculated showed a wide difference from experimentally reported values. The same was true for chloroprene as was reported by Santhanam and Sobhanadri³³. According to Basu's analysis, theoretical calculation was done only on single charge transfer molecule made up of one chloranil and one hydrocarbon whereas in the experimental field there are always some chance of each chlorine being influenced by other polynuclear hydrocarbons from the neighbouring crystal sites.

Conclusion :

This review is confined to the NQR studies on charge transfer complexes. It has found application in a wide range of chemical compounds, and it is becoming as important as NMR studies. Both physicists and chemists are using this as one of their tools in exploring the molecular structure of compounds.

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